

Book Presentation

Smol, J.P. 2023. *Lakes in the Anthropocene: Reflections on tracking ecosystem change in the Arctic*. Excellence in Ecology Book Series, International Ecology Institute (ECI), Oldendorf/Luhe, Germany. 438 pp. ISBN 978-3-946729-30-3 ISSN 0932-2205. €50 - plus postage (print edition, hardcover)

In a book that is part memoir and part textbook, renowned limnologist John Smol reflects on his 35+ years of aquatic research in the Arctic. Working primarily on the limnology and environmental histories of lakes and ponds, he emphasizes the need for using appropriate spatial and temporal scales to understand the effects of natural and anthropogenic stressors. An overriding theme is the critical role that accelerated climate change plays as a “threat multiplier”. The book pays homage to some of the pioneers of Arctic limnology using archival photographs before summarizing a diverse array of paleoenvironmental studies that he and his colleagues have led. Highlighted research includes collaborations with Indigenous knowledge holders and archeologists, tracking past ocean flooding events, the repercussions of permafrost thaw, the effects of pollutants from both local and distant sources, as well as tracking long-term changes in salmon and bird populations. Smol emphasizes the importance of using diverse sources of information, the role that personal relationships can play in successful collaborative programs, and issues linked to environmental justice for Northern peoples.

Table of Contents

Introduction

Dedication

Preface and Acknowledgement

- 1 Warnings from lake mud: Arctic lakes and ponds in the Anthropocene
- 2 The pioneers: early studies on High Arctic limnology
- 3 A primer on paleolimnology
- 4 The power of ice: Arctic lakes on the frontline of climate change
- 5 The ‘early peoples’: pre-Anthropocene impacts
- 6 Marine storm surges on inland waters: ‘different ways of knowing’
- 7 Permafrost thaw: sinks, slumps, and sumps
- 8 Northern communities: the challenges of living in a cold climate
- 9 ‘Sledgehammers’: impacts of northern mining on aquatic ecosystems
- 10 What happens in the South does not necessarily stay in the South: long-range transport of pollutants to the Arctic
- 11 Salmon and sediments: biovectors moving nutrients and contaminants from oceans to lakes
- 12 Is paleolimnology for the birds? Arctic seabirds as biovectors of nutrients and contaminants
- 13 Crossing ecological thresholds and disappearing ecosystems: ‘the fierce urgency of now’

Literature cited

As a laureate of the [International Ecology Institute Prize](#) John Smol’s newest book is published in the [Excellence in Ecology Book Series](#). The International Ecology Institute is a not-for-profit (i.e., no royalties, etc.), and hence the relatively low price of €50 (plus postage). A web page on the [PEARL](#) website has links to the 2-page flyer (library recommendations) as well as other information on the [book](#).

Orders can be placed from the Distributor ([Natural History Bookstore, NHBS](#)) or directly from the [International Ecology Institute](#).

Note the ECI web site states: Students are entitled to a 40% reduction, provided they are able to supply written proof of their status. If you have any further questions, please contact eebooks@int-res.com.

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10324557>

